

BLE Transit Beacons

Increasing accuracy of transit notifications through BLE Advertisements.

Jonas Arndt

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v1.0

Abstract

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1 Introduction

When Location Tracking is not reliable, like underground transports. We can increase the accuracy of transit notifications from apps like Google Maps and similar.

A User traveling in an unfamiliar region could use an app supporting this standard to get audible notifications when the vehicle they are currently traveling on is about to reach the station they need to get off at. Especially on underground services the location accuracy is bad enough that the vehicle may have already left the station before an app has detected the user arriving at that station.

Without communications from the transit vehicle, apps need to guess at the current state of the vehicle by analyzing the device location. This analysis is already error prone, introducing further errors through coarse device locations only worsens the accuracy.

Most apps use [GTFS Schedule](#) and [GTFS-RT](#) feeds to schedule journeys, so a lot of information is already available.

2 Overview

The information about the vehicle state is already available in the on board systems of the vehicle, so instead of indirectly guessing about it based on the location it is more accurate to use it directly. By adding BLE beacons to the vehicle, we can broadcast this information to all interested parties.

The BLE 4.0 specification only allow a limited number of Bytes to be used for custom data. In our use case we get to use up to 13 for custom data, which limits the amount of information transmitted.

The data provided by the broadcasts described in this document are only supposed to supplement data of already scheduled journeys. The data broadcasted is consciously not enough to schedule a complete trip.

This solution assumes access to GTFS feeds, without the context of those the data provided by the beacons is not helpful.

The use of the data transmitted is up to the consumer. The data provided by implementing devices and entities is on a best effort basis, it must not be used for safety- or security-critical decisions.

3 Technical Specification

We only define a data type contract for use in BLE advertisements using the Service UUID `9c9ba9f8-b598-4ee3-a8f6-2131e6731a55`. Conforming Beacons must advertise as non-connectable and don't transmit flags, this is needed to achieve a useable payload of 13 Bytes.

Figure 1: Overview of the Communication channels used.

The onboard vehicle computer communicates its current state to the BLE beacon which updates the state broadcasted when applicable. All multi byte values use little-endian byte ordering.

If this document talks about a station it refers to the same entity as a GTFS stop with `location_type=1`.

3.1 Packet format

All ranges are inclusive (e.g. 0..2 denotes 0, 1, and 2).

Packets have the following content.

Byte(s)	Meaning
0..2	Operator Id
3	Packet type
4..n	Type dependent body

3.2 Packet types

We define the following packet types:

Type	Meaning
0x00	Invalid - do not use
0x01	Stopped at station
0x02	Leaving station
0x03	Traveling to station
0x04	Arriving at station
0xf0..0xff	Reserved for use by the operator

Each packet type can have a different layout and length for its body data.

With publication the internal structure of each type becomes immutable. All implementers need to silently drop packages with unrecognized types.

Operator specific packages need to be treated as unrecognized if the operator id is not associated with any definitions.

Beacons should avoid skipping states, receivers must handle skipped states gracefully.

3.2.1 0x01..0x04 Simple mode

The states 1-4 share a common body format.

Byte(s)	Meaning
4..6	Trip id
7..8	Route id
9..10	Station id

Trip, route and station ids are operator defined opaque mappings to their GTFS equivalent. An operator supporting this standard is expected to supply these ids with their GTFS feed.

The trip id must be supplied by the extension field `ble_tb_id` in `trips.txt`. The route id must be supplied by the extension field `ble_tb_id` in `routes.txt`. The station id must be supplied by the extension field `ble_tb_id` in `stops.txt`, the station id is only required for stations, platforms may also have a `ble_tb_id`. The `ble_tb_id` is to be encoded as a decimal representation of an integer that fits into an unsigned 24 or 16 bit number respectively.

Because the file already disambiguates the entity type, all three files use the same column name.

3.3 Operator ID

The operator id is a 24 bit code, prefixed by the ISO 3166-1 country code. This document only prescribes the most general prefix - the country code. The remaining 14 bits can be structured in any way the local authority decides. It is expected that operators get together to formalize a standard.

Bits	meaning
23..14	ISO 3166-1 numeric country code
13..0	country specific identification

3.4 Transmission Interval

A Beacon should repeat its advertisement at least once every 1000ms, but where possible the interval should be shrunk to the smallest allowed value according to the BLE 4.0 specification.

Especially in train and subway installations where power consumption is of little to no concern, beacons should advertise every 100ms. The goal is to increase the probability of receivers getting to see the advertisement.

3.5 State Hold Timings

To allow all receivers to pick up on a state change, a vehicle must not exit or change their state in the first 5s after entering it.

The goal of the timings should be to allow clients enough time to detect the state change, notify the user, and let the user leave the vehicle stress free.

The “arriving at” state is the most critical to the user experience, therefore beacon implementers should take steps not to skip it. It should also be entered at least 30s before coming to a stop.

On the other hand beacons must not enter “arriving at” while still standing at the previous station to avoid confusion.

4 Technical Notes

4.1 Boarding detection

The app should assume the user boarded the correct vehicle, but continuously validate this assumption for the duration of the journey. Initial boarding is confirmed by the first vehicle broadcasting the route required by the next leg of the scheduled journey from the boarding station.

Boarding validation is not a one-time event. The app should flag a potential erroneous boarding if broadcasts from the confirmed trip are no longer observed, but another trip is observed leaving the current station. If broadcasts from a different trip are observed arriving at stations inconsistent with the planned journey, the app should similarly flag a potential erroneous boarding. Both conditions may also indicate a vehicle substitution by the operator rather than a user error.

4.2 RSSI

RSSI may be a good indicator for the physical distance to a beacon, but it is not overly accurate and the general reach of Bluetooth signals is less than the usual distance between stations, therefore visibility implies the vehicle is close enough to be relevant for the user to board. So apps should rely more on pure visibility of the beacons than RSSI.

5 Future Extensions

In the future this standard could be expanded to allow stations to broadcast arriving vehicles, including their ids and route ids.

6 Further Resources

A small POC for the [Beacon](#) and [App](#) can be found in the [BLE Transit Beacons](#) GitHub Organization.